

EFFECT OF LIFESTYLE AND EATING BEHAVIOURS ON CHILDHOOD OBESITY IN GEN-ALPHA (2010-2024)

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Abstract: “Obesity or Overweight” is defined as the Excess fat Deposition in the tissues and body. Generation Alpha refers to the children born during “2010-2024” time period, also called as ‘Digital Native’. Due to the Vast global Technological advancements such as Rapid Urbanization and immense Digitalization, lead to the Extreme sedentary Lifestyles, Screen Exposure, High processed food Consumption, all these contribute to obesity Prevalence in children Especially. The sudden surge in obesity rates contributes to a global challenge, which needs to be addressed together. Therefore, The study involves Questionnaire of 200 children aged between 5-15 Yrs, aims to investigate the Effect of Lifestyle and Eating behaviours on childhood Obesity in Generation Alpha. The Data compiled using research statistics, and the findings represent a significant Relationship between the Lifestyle and dietary behaviours on the obesity prevalence in Gen-alpha children. The study reveals that the parental monitoring and influence play a crucial role in shaping children's Lifestyle and behaviours.

Key words: Generation Alpha, Digitalization, obesity, Eating behaviours, Lifestyle

Introduction:

Obesity, Historically Once considered as a symbolic sign of prosperity, even now in some places of the world. Also, Considered as a Determinant of one's good health, wealth and well-nourished person. However, it's now a potential to various chronic health conditions. Obesity is a chronic complex disease defined by the excessive accumulation of fat in the tissues and body, that can impair health and lead to chronic health conditions and severe diseases. Most importantly 'Childhood Obesity' is prevalent in the 21st century, especially among generation alpha. It has been merged as a significant public health concern globally, with rates rising dramatically over the past few decades. Obesity is a condition, when the body mass index (BMI) is above ≥ 30 kg/m². Additionally, A person is considered to be Overweight having a BMI of ≥ 25 kg/m². There are several contributing factors to 'obesity', based on their nature and potential of control. “Intrinsic factors” are those causes which are genetics, any endocrine disorders, medications, and due to other causes like energy imbalance, hormonal imbalances and so on, which requires much care and supervision to control the inbody factors and is a relatively great time-consuming process to cure and recover from it. On the other hand, “Extrinsic factors” usually consider environment, our diet, sedentary lifestyle, lack of physical activity, abnormal sleep wake cycles, Socio-economic conditions, standard of living, exposure to digital media and electronic devices (screen time), parental influence and relationship, social influence, stress, depression, and many other. All these factors they subject the children eight folds greater risks of developing childhood obesity, which in later life puts them on the verge of developing chronic health conditions.

Aim:

The Research aims to investigate the Effect of Lifestyle and Eating behaviours and it's Correlation on the prevalence of obesity in Gen-Alpha children.

Objectives

The study primarily aims to

- Analyse the changes in lifestyle and eating behaviors in Gen-alpha children.
- To investigate the impact of digitalization on eating patterns of children.
- To analyse the screen time among Gen-alpha children.
- To pro

Review Of Literature:

The systematic review by Rafaela et.al , investigates the association between dietary habits and the risk of developing childhood obesity. The dietary practices observed are classified diversely as (1) significant Obesogenic foods and (2) weakest Obesity associated foods. The study presents that a lower portion of significant Obesogenic foods will potentially reduce the obesity developing risk. This study explored by Caicui Ding, Jing Fan, et al. investigates the relationships that PA, SB, sleep, and diet significantly influence adiposity proportions in Chinese children and adolescents. A multi behavioural approach for guidelines is associated with a lower risk of overweight/obesity. The study by Warly Neves de araujo demonstrates the negative factors contributing to the triggering of childhood obesity are: passive habits like little or no physical activity, the large number of hours spent in front of TV, video game, and Other electronic devices this integrated with poor dietary habits including high fat and sugar products and lack of physical exercise all these factors altogether reflects to a high prevalence of obesity in children. The study by Zong, et al., findings reflects that screen time exposure was significantly associated with myopia in children and adolescents. Especially, screen time exposure from computers may have the most detrimental impact on myopia.

Methodology:

A structured questionnaire administered to gather information on dietary habits, physical activity levels, screen time, family dynamics, and socioeconomic status among Children aged 5-12YRS (Children and students of Generation alpha). A sample of 200 with children aged 5-12 yrs, recruited from schools and communities. Data collected through Convenient sampling, snowball sampling methods. The Qualitative data is collected through Review articles, Journals and available latest data and statistics from the sources like Pubmed, NIH, NLM, Google scholar, The data compiled using research statistics methods like ANOVA, correlation, to investigate the impact of lifestyle and obesity among generation - alpha children.

Results And Discussion:

Post-HOCS Test - Anova Multiple Comparison Test	
Dependent Variable	Sig
Consume	0.44
Skip Meals	.002
Screen Time	0.008,0.036
Meal Time	0.006,0.011
Physical Activity	0.008
Screen Effect	<0.001
Device before bed	0.025

One-Way Anova Test	
Dependent Variable	Sig
Skip Meals	.013
Screen Time	0.043
Increase in screen Time past 6 Months	0.040
Emotional Eating	<0.01
Type of Physical Activity	0.018
Duration of Physical Activity	0.016
Screen Effect	0.001

The “ANOVA Multiple comparison (post hocs) Test” results represent significant relation between food cravings (especially outside junk and processed food), consumption patterns (irregular unhealthy eating patterns) and parental support (encouraging the children towards outside food consumption) on eating patterns of children, thus representing that parents are encouraging children for junk food consumption, thus raising the incidence of obesity and lifestyle disorders among Gen-alpha children.

The ANOVA test represents significant association between the exposure to screen time (leading to sedentary lifestyle), new food choices (acceptance to new foods), emotional eating with respect to parental support and monitoring (encouraging children to have unhealthy foods, and more screen time) on eating behaviors in Gen-alpha children.

	Correlation	Eating pattern		past	digitalization	parent
Spearman's rho	Eating pattern	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.029	-.118	-.050
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.683	.097	.480
		N	200	200	200	200
	past	Correlation Coefficient	-.029	1.000	.072	-.044
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.683	.	.314	.535
		N	200	200	200	200
	digitalization	Correlation Coefficient	-.118	.072	1.000	.209**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.097	.314	.	.003
		N	200	200	200	200
	parent	Correlation Coefficient	-.050	-.044	.209**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.480	.535	.003	.
		N	200	200	200	200

Table-1.3: Spearman's Rho Correlation Test for Lifestyle Behaviors and Parental Influence

The "Spearman's rho correlation test" analysis depicts that, eating patterns shows a negative correlation with physical activity and screen time, digitalization and parental monitoring. Also, physical activity and Digitalization shares a positive correlation with eating patterns, parental monitoring. It shows a positive correlation with digitalization. Thus, it represents a negative influence of parental monitoring and the screen time exposure on the eating patterns of children, therefore, leading to lifestyle disorders.

CONCLUSION:

The Research findings represents that Eating behaviours, Excess Digital Engagement, and Increased Sedentary Lifestyle and Parental influence has impact on the Gen-alpha children, and also suggests that there is high risk of obesity in future. The study recommends to reduce the screen exposure, to increase the physical activity duration, and encourage consumption of nutritious meals, and engage in family-based activities and games for children and thus encourage healthy lifestyle and eating behaviours of children.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- The parents should strictly monitor the digital time exposure of children, and limit the screen exposure to less than 2 hours as advised by WHO.
- The parents and schools should provide education awareness and tools to enhance the physical activity, sleep and nutritional status of the children.
- The children should be actively involved in family-based activities, emotional support, physical activity games and active parental monitoring (e.g., screen time rules, meal tracking) to avoid the sedentary and unhealthy lifestyle.

FUTURE RESEARCH RECOMMENDATIONS:

The Study suggests further future research on extent of influence of digital engagement and modern lifestyle on the obesity incidence in the Generation Alpha, also on current modern Generations backed with extreme technology.

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